

Studies on 8-Hydroxycoumarin

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8-Hydroxycoumarin on formylation affords the 7-formyl derivative and on the Friedel-Crafts acylation, the 7-acetyl derivative, also obtained by the Fries migration of 8-acetoxycoumarin. Furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-7,8-coumarin has been synthesised from the 7-acetyl derivative. On the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and benzylamine, 8-hydroxycoumarin furnishes 2'H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-7,8-coumarin which has been degraded to 8-hydroxy-7-benzylaminomethylcoumarin by heating with HCl.

Dey and Kutti¹ studied the nitration and halogenation of 8-hydroxycoumarin and Mauthner² studied the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 8-methoxycoumarin. Very recently Kaufman and Russey³ have synthesised furo-2'-methyl-4',5'-7,8-coumarin, starting with 8-hydroxycoumarin.

8-Hydroxycoumarin has now been subjected to some other reactions with a view to studying the pattern of substitution and to synthesising coumarino- α - and- γ -pyrones and furocoumarins.

On formylation with hexamethylenetetramine, this coumarin afforded the 7-formyl derivative in low yield and on the Friedel-Crafts acylation, the 7-acetyl derivative, which was also obtained on the Fries migration of 8-acetoxycoumarin. The Dakin oxidation of the formyl and the acetyl derivatives furnished the known 7,8-dihydroxycoumarin⁴.

Furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-7,8-coumarin (I) has now been synthesised by condensation of 8-hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarin with bromoacetic ester, hydrolysis of the ester obtained to the corresponding acid, and cyclisation and decarboxylation of the acid by heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.

On the Mannich reaction with formaldehyde and benzylamine, 8-hydroxycoumarin gave a product, insoluble in alkali, to which the 2'H-3'-benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-7,8-coumarin (II) structure has been assigned². On heating with ethanolic HCl,

1. Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India, 1940, 6, 641.

2. J. prakt. Chem., 1939, 152, 23.

3. J. Org. Chem., 1962, 27, 671.

4. Pechmann, Ber., 1834, 17, 929.

the compound (II) afforded 8-hydroxy-7-benzylaminomethylcoumarin and formaldehyde. The former, on Sommelet reaction, afforded 8-hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin.

The Pechmann condensation of 8-hydroxycoumarin with acetoacetic ester in presence of either sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide or by refluxing in diphenyl ether⁶ did not succeed.

EXPERIMENTAL

8-Hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin.—A mixture of 8-hydroxycoumarin (1.62 g., 0.01*M*) and hexamethylenetetramine (5.62 g., 0.04*M*) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 7 hrs. HCl (1:1) was then added and the heating continued for further 2 hrs. The product obtained on extraction with ether crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 238-40°. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 3.2. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 63.1; H, 3.1%). It developed an intense reddish brown coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

The above coumarin (2.29 g., 0.01*M*) was treated with hydrogen peroxide (100 vol., 1ml) in 5% NaOH solution and stirred for 3 to 4 hrs. at 0° to 5°. On acidification, the product separating was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 256°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 7,8-dihydroxycoumarin was not depressed.

8-Hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarin.—8-Hydroxycoumarin (1.62 g., 0.01*M*), mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.2 g., 0.04*M*) and acetic anhydride (3 ml), was heated in an oil bath at 140-50° for 2 hrs. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from ethanol in brownish yellow needles, m.p. 201-202°. (Found: C, 64.7; H, 3.9. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.7; H, 3.9%). It gave an intense reddish brown coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

The same compound was obtained when 8-acetoxycoumarin⁷ (2.2g., 0.01*M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.2g., 0.04*M*) were mixed thoroughly and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath. The temperature was slowly raised to 170° during 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual.

Ethyl 7-Acetyl-8-coumarin-oxycacetate.—8-Hydroxy-7-acetylcoumarin (2.g.), bromoacetic ester (1.6 g.), and potassium carbonate (1.3 g.) were refluxed in acetone for 4 hrs. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145-48°. (Found: C, 62.3; H, 5.1. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.0; H, 4.8%).

7-Acetyl-8-coumarin-oxycacetic Acid.—The above ester on hydrolysis by heating with 5% NaOH gave 7-acetyl-8-coumarin-oxycacetic acid which crystallised from ethanol in white plates, m.p. 235-36°. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 3.9. $C_{13}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 59.5; H, 3.8%).

Furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-7,8-coumarin.—The above acid (1.5 g.) was heated with sodium acetate (1g.) and acetic anhydride (3 ml) on a wire gauge for 30 minutes. The product

5. Cf. Patel and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 595.

6. Desai *et al.*, *J. M. S. Univ., Baroda*, 1955, **4**, 1.

7. Bohme, *Ber.*, 1939, **72B**, 2130.

crystallised from ethanol in white shining plates, m.p. 146-48°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 4.1. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.0; H, 4.0%).

2'-H-3'-Benzyl-3',4'-dihydro-1',3'-oxazino-5',6'-7,8-coumarin.—8-Hydroxycoumarin (2 g., 0.015M), benzylamine (5 ml), and formalin (7 ml) were dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) and refluxed for 2 hrs. on a water bath. The product separating was crystallised from ethanol in shining crystals, m.p. 186-87°. (Found: C, 74.0; H, 5.1; N, 4.4. $C_{18}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.1; N, 4.7%).

8-Hydroxy-7-benzylaminomethylcoumarin.—The above oxazino derivative (1.5 g.) was refluxed with ethanolic HCl (1:1) for 2 hrs. and the product obtained on neutralising with ammonia was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 143-44°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 5.3; N, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 72.6; H, 5.3; N, 4.9%).

This Mannich base (2.6 g.) and hexamethylenetetramine (5.6 g.) in glacial acetic acid were heated for 6 hrs. on a steam bath and then HCl (conc., 15 ml) was added and the heating continued for 2 hrs. The product obtained on ether extraction crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 238-40°. Mixed m.p. with 8-hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin was not depressed.

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